

Recommended citation: Becker, P. (2020). Digitalization of Engineering Mechanics Problems Applying the Stack-Concept. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 598-606). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14653977](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653977).

DIGITALIZATION OF ENGINEERING MECHANICS PROBLEMS APPLYING THE STACK-CONCEPT

P. Becker

University of Applied Sciences
Karlsruhe, Germany

Conference Key Areas: *E-Learning, Online-Learning*

Keywords: *Digitalization, Exercises, Homework, Engineering Mechanics*

ABSTRACT

It is widely accepted that in Mechanics and other technical courses students need to work on problems by themselves for a good learning outcome. The assignment of homework seems to be a reasonable method of making students deal with problems. The downsides are big efforts for organization and evaluation of the homework. Considering that many students simply copy their homework from fellow students, the effort seems questionable and keeps many professors from assigning homework.

Improvements can be obtained by digitalizing Mechanics problems applying the STACK-concept. STACK is a free Plug-In for electronic learning systems like Moodle or Ilias. It is backed up by a Computer Algebra System and is therefore able to interpret and evaluate mathematical expressions (matrices, equations, etc.). So far mainly mathematicians apply it for mathematical education. But STACK can generally be applied in any discipline where mathematics is involved, which is the case in most courses of engineering education.

STACK additionally contains some interesting features, i.e. can produce random numbers, so every student gets different values and is therefore forced to work on his own individual problem. Evaluation is completely done by the system. After putting in an answer the student can check his answer for correctness. Depending on his answer the student may receive an individual feedback, which can be provided by a response tree. The digitalized problems may also be extended by interactive graphical elements.

First implementations of STACK-Problems in homework assignments show promising results and good acceptance by the students.

1 INTRODUCTION

There seems to be agreement that students not only should attend the lectures but also need to work on problems themselves for consolidation of knowledge and a good learning outcome (i.e. [1]). The usual way to do so is to assign homeworks. Homework is considered to enhance student knowledge, improve retention and master concepts taught in the lectures.

To activate students working on problems, homeworks are often mandatory prerequisites for participation in the final exam or bonus points are awarded. Mandatory homework assignments are not so common in Germany compared to other European states. The main reasons for this are that

- the correction of homework is usually involved with a tremendous correctional effort and
- students often copy the homeworks from each other questioning the concept.

Still the engineering education proved to be successful over the decades since most students have been self-reliant enough to work on problems themselves without being enforced to do so.

Fig. 1: Percentage of young people in Germany starting studying in their age group [2]

In the last couple of years students behavior as changed with students starting studying at a younger age and therefore less self-reliant due to political changes during the last couple of years in Germany [3]:

- In 2011 the “Wehrpflicht”, the duty of young men to serve for the military, was suspended.

- In the years from 2011 to 2013 most German regions cancelled a school year enabling students to finish school and qualify for university after 12 years of school instead of 13.

Furthermore the percentage of young people studying has increased from 37% in 2002 to almost 60% nowadays (Fig. 1). This is especially promoted by the German industry, which is permanent seeking for young people with a good technical education, and German politics thus taking the necessary actions. Due to these changes adjustments in teaching are recommendable to be able to better support the students. For example, university teachers should assign homework on a more regular basis. The computer aided assessment system STACK has proved to be a wonderful tool to implement online homework and make students work on technical problems.

2 THE PROBLEM-TYPE STACK

STACK is a free plug-in for electronic learning systems like Moodle or Ilias. Next to the variety of online assessments already offered it enables a completely new type of online problems. STACK stands for „**S**ystem for **T**eaching and **A**ssessment using a **C**omputer Algebra **K**ernel”. It has been developed by the British Mathematician Chris Sangwin [4] from the University of Edinburgh.

In the meanwhile STACK is used by quite some universities throughout Europe and probably also on other continents. So far it is mainly applied by mathematicians in the mathematical education of students. But generally STACK may be applied in any discipline where mathematics is involved, especially in classical engineering courses like Mechanics, Electrotechnics or Thermodynamics.

What makes STACK so unique compared to previous kinds of online assessment systems is that it contains some special features with some of them listed here:

Computer Algebra System

In the traditional type of online-assessment students put in a string as answer which is compared to an answer string provided by the developer of the problem. Since STACK is backed up by the Computer Algebra System “Maxima” mathematical expressions like equations, matrices or sets can be put in as answer. Usually there are different possibilities how to put in a mathematical expression. A constant factor for example may be placed at the beginning or at the end of an expression. STACK doesn’t care about this since it is able to evaluate mathematical equity of answer and solution.

A validation button is additionally offered, enabling the students to check, how their answers are interpreted by the system.

Randomized Problems

When assigning homework in Germany a common problem is, that students simply copy their solutions. Compared to states like UK or USA a thing called “academic

honour” does not exist. In Germany students often treat it as a sport to cheat the professor.

The possibility of randomizing problems by giving the students different numerical values is therefore a wonderful thing. The times, where homework results are spread in WhatsApp-Groups are gone forever. Each student gets his own individual problem and therefore is forced to deal with it and work on it.

Individual Feedback

Right after putting in an answer students can check their result for correctness by applying the Check-Button and receive feedback immediately. The students may then correct their answer if it proves to be incorrect. The number of re-submission of results can be limited though.

If the result of the student proves to be false the student may also receive individual feedback depending on his answer. The feedback is provided by a response tree, which has to be created by the developer of the problem. Instructors usually know about common errors of their students and can make the system give special feedback and maybe advice to the students, which should enable them to finally solve the problem.

If a problem is partially solved students may receive partial credit.

Interactive Graphical Elements

In the meanwhile STACK-problems can be extended by interactive graphical elements. Possibilities will be shown in a later chapter.

3 APPLICATION TO ENGINEERING MECHANICS PROBLEMS

More than 100 STACK-problems were developed in early 2018 and tentatively tested in the summer-semester of 2018 in a “Mechanics of Materials”-course. The students had to complete online homework, working weekly on 3 to 5 online problems. They had to collect 80% of the maximum number of points awarded for correctly solving the problems to be permitted to participate in the final exam.

When implemented in STACK typical “Mechanics-of-Materials”-problems can usually be separated into various partial problems, which build up on each other as shown in figure 2. In this problem the students have to finally determine the maximum tensile and compressive stresses for a beam with the given profile stressed by a bending moment. The numerical values below the graph are randomly chosen from intervals by the system.

To be able to calculate the stresses, various cross-sectional quantities have to be determined first: Especially the axial area-moment of inertia needs to be known, which of course can only be computed if the location of the area center is determined in advance.

So by splitting the problem into various parts the students are kind of guided through the problem. They can right away see the steps necessary to solve it. By repeatedly doing so they get a certain routine on solving this type of problem.

TM2-Problem 3-05

A beam with the sketched profile is stressed by a bending moment of $M_y = 80 \text{ kNm}$.

Determine the maximum tensile and compressive stresses.

Given: $b_1 = 340 \text{ mm}$, $b_2 = 160 \text{ mm}$, $h = 300 \text{ mm}$, $t = 30 \text{ mm}$

a) Distance of Area Center from Top Edge of Profile: $\zeta_s =$ mm

b) Area Moments of Inertia: $I_y =$ cm^4
 $I_z =$ cm^4

c) Axial Section Modulus: $W_y =$ cm^3

d) Max. Tensile and Compressive Stress:

$\sigma_{t,\max} =$ N/mm^2

$\sigma_{c,\max} =$ N/mm^2

Prüfen

Fig. 2: Typical Mechanics-of-Materials STACK-Problem

In STACK-based online problems the students can check their results after each step and receive immediate feedback by clicking the “Prüfen”(“Check”)-Button (Figure 2). If the feedback is positive (“Correct”), the student can be very sure about continuing the problem with the correct partial result, which he will need to solve the next part of the problem. If the students entry proves to be incorrect he can overwork the problem and reenter the solution until positive approval is given. The student may even receive feedback by the system as generated by the developer of the STACK-problem. Depending on the students answer the feedback can be very specific as can be seen in figure 3.

In the problem shown in figure 2 it would have been possible just to ask for the final answer which are the requested stresses. However, if students enter an incorrect final answer it might become very difficult to find out, in which part of the problem the error occurred. It is therefore much more efficient, helpful and motivating for the students to split the problem into several parts.

TM2-Problem 3-05

A beam with the sketched profile is stressed by a bending moment of $M_y = 80 \text{ kNm}$. Determine the maximum tensile and compressive stresses.

Given: $b_1 = 340 \text{ mm}$, $b_2 = 160 \text{ mm}$, $h = 300 \text{ mm}$, $t = 30 \text{ mm}$

a) Distance of Area Center from Top Edge of Profile: $\zeta_S =$ mm

Correct!

b) Area Moments of Inertia: $I_y =$ cm^4

The answer is not correct.

You missed to consider the parallel-axis theorem!

Fig. 3: Positive approval and specific feedback by the system

4 INTERACTIVE GRAPHICAL ELEMENTS

New web technologies and further development of electronic learning systems have simplified the use of interactive graphical elements in mathematical and technical online problems. By embedding JavaScript based JSXGraph-Elements STACK-problems can be expanded by interactive graphical elements, which can be developed with manageable effort [5]. JSXGraph is a JavaScript-Library, which helps to develop interactive graphics with little code and minimal programming knowledge. The graphics may be embedded on HTML-sites and displayed on all common web-browsers without additional software [6].

Graphical solutions are widely accepted to deepen the students understanding of Engineering Mechanics. Interactive graphical parts lead to a diversification of STACK-problems. Graphical methods in Mechanics are for example applied when adding forces in force diagrams in Statics or adding velocities and accelerations in diagrams in Dynamics. Instantaneous center of velocity diagrams can widen the students views of what is happening in a mechanisms. Again individual feedback depending on the students solution is possible (Figure 4).

Although interactive graphical elements are a clear enrichment for digital exercises there is need of further development. As the procedure is different depending on the

electronic learning system there should be a more standardized approach for embedding JavaScript-elements in STACK-problems. This would simplify the import and export of problems into other systems to generate a fruitful exchange between universities.

TM3-Problem-4-z1

Rod AB of the robot arm is rotating with angular velocity $\dot{\alpha}$, rod BC with angular velocity $\dot{\beta}$ at the shown instant.

Given:
 $\alpha = 40^\circ$, $\beta = 70^\circ$, $\dot{\alpha} = 0.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\dot{\beta} = 0.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $l = 0.5 \text{ m}$

Graphically determine the velocity \vec{v}_C of point C in the velocity diagram below.

Note: Select an arbitrary starting point. All vectors can be arbitrarily shifted, twisted, extended or contracted. Absolute value and direction of vectors are displayed.

Graphically determine the velocity \vec{v}_C of point C in the velocity diagram below.

Richtig!

Directions of Vectors are correct.

Absolute Values of Vectors are correct.

Note: Select an arbitrary starting point. All vectors can be arbitrarily shifted, twisted, extended or contracted. Absolute value and direction of vectors are displayed.

Velocity Diagram

Velocity Diagram

Fig. 4: Problem with interactive graphic element (left), solution with feedback (right)

5 EVALUATION BY STUDENTS

Starting back in 2018 STACK-Problems have been developed for the three common courses in Engineering Mechanics (Statics, Mechanics of Materials, Dynamics) at the University of Applied Sciences Karlsruhe. In the Mechanics of Materials course STACK-problems have been employed for four semesters, in Dynamics only for one semester so far. During the ongoing Covid-19-Semester, where no presence teaching has been possible, it has been deployed for all EM-courses.

As can be seen in figure 5 opinions are diversified with students expressing positive and also negative comments about having to work on Online-STACK-Problems. Positive voices mostly emphasized the gain because of immediate feedback and the benefit of continuous exercising. Negative comments were almost entirely because of the time-consuming aspect.

The attitude changed in the ongoing Covid-19-Semester with almost all students commenting positively about online exercises and therefore obviously recognizing the benefit.

Generally the students seem to accept this kind of online-exercise. Many young people love to play computer games, solving problems on the screen and getting awarded by collecting points. Online homework is not so much different from that so there should be motivation for this kind of exercise.

Fig. 5: Evaluation by Students

6 SUMMARY

Not only in the times of Covid-19-Virus STACK has proved to be an extremely valuable tool in the technical education especially for young students in early semesters since it has been introduced at the University of Applied Sciences Karlsruhe. New features like evaluation of mathematical expressions, individual feedback, randomized numerical values and graphical elements implemented into the STACK-concept widen the possibilities for this kind of E-learning. Positive comments in the semester-evaluation show, that the students accept this kind of exercise and see the necessity of working on problems in addition to the lecture to improve their learning outcome, although some students complained about the increase in the workload. In many technical disciplines different kind of problems can be generated for fruitful use. Interactive graphical elements contribute to a higher motivation and understanding of the students. The development of STACK-problems is time-consuming and has to be done very carefully since possible errors would only confuse the students, but the effort is well worth it.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been supported by the “Verbund der Stifter” (“Group of Donators”) of the University of Applied Sciences Karlsruhe.

REFERENCES

- [1] Williams, A (2012), Online Homeworks vs. Traditional Homework: Statistical Anxiety and Self Efficacy in an Educational Statistics Course. *Journal of Technology Innovations in Statistics Education*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 1-19.
- [2] Entwicklung der Studienanfängerquoten in Deutschland von 2001 bis 2018, From: <http://de.statistik/daten/72005/umfrage/entwicklung-der-studienanfängerquote/> , accessed on 04/13/2020
- [3] Statistisches Bundesamt (2020), Reihe 4.1 Studierende an Hochschulen.
- [4] Sangwin, C (2013), Computer Aided Assessment of Mathematics, Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- [5] Vasko, M (2018), Interaktive grafische Aufgaben mit STACK und JSXGraph, *Beiträge zum Mathematik-Unterricht 2018*, pp. 1855-1858.
- [6] Gerhäuser, M, Wassermann, A, Valentin, B (2010), JSXGraph – Dynamic Mathematics with JavaScript, *Journal for Technology in Mathematics Education*, Vol. 17, No. 4, pp. 211-216.